

Special prevention efforts for women's wellbeing at work focused on physical ergonomics in the health-care sector

Kersti LOREN

Swedish Work Environment Authority, Göteborg, Sweden

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1. Introduction

The Swedish Government has commissioned the Swedish Work Environment Authority to develop and implement specific interventions aimed at preventing women from being excluded from working life because of work-related problems. Physical ergonomics has been/is the aim of one of the projects in this intervention.

The project has the aim to prevent ill health and premature exit from the labor market because of musculoskeletal disorders among women.

The project consists of three parts:

- Information, gathering and dissemination
- Methodological and professional development and
- Supervision

2. Methods

The supervision of 2013 has taken part in the health-care sector, and has been focused on physical ergonomics in manual handling of patients and the necessity of performing risk assessments in these situations.

Methods easy to use have been hard to find. A new information brochure has been developed, and the Dutch method Tilthermometer has been introduced to the employers. Also the Finnish method PTAI has been shown to them.

3. Results

At the moment we are writing the report underlying the presentation at the NES conference. We have checked 682 companies and businesses in the health-care sector. Over 70% of them got demands to improve their working environment.